

REMEDYING DISPLACEMENT IN FROZEN CONFLICTS: LESSONS FROM THE CASE OF CYPRUS*

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the jurisprudence of the European Court of Human Rights, in order to assess the effectiveness of the remedies provided and procedures followed by the Immovable Property Commission (henceforth, IPC), a mechanism that was established by Turkey in order to remedy displaced Greek Cypriots. It recommends changes for the improvement of the IPC and argues that with their adoption, the Commission could act as a blueprint for the establishment of similar remedying bodies in other frozen conflicts as well. Such institutions are not only important in terms of states' compliance with their human rights obligations, but can also contribute to the resolution of the underlying conflict itself.

Keywords: Forced displacement, frozen conflicts, effective remedies.

I. INTRODUCTION

Over the last decades, the European Court of Human Rights (henceforth, ECtHR or Court) has adjudicated a number of cases where applicants, who have been forcibly displaced from their properties as a result of violent conflict, seek a remedy for the violation of their rights.[‡] This jurisprudence has been particularly influential in those societies, which years after the ceasefire that ended the violence, are still divided by frozen conflicts not yet resolved through comprehensive peace agreements. Several such frozen conflicts exist in Europe and so far, the Court has dealt with cases relating to forced displacement in two of them – Cyprus and Naborno-Karabakh. The ECtHR's consistent response in these cases has been that the respondent state has an obligation to remedy displaced people, especially when the negotiations for the settlement of the conflict have been ongoing, yet remain unfruitful, for years. These remedies, it was accepted in *Demopoulos v. Turkey*[§] and subsequently reiterated in *Chiragov v. Armenia*^{**} and *Sargsyan v. Azerbaijan*,^{††} should be provided to the displaced population by a domestic institution with a special mandate to act accordingly.

In light of the numerous examples of forced displacement as a result of frozen conflicts, and the possibility that it can act as a blueprint for them, this article examines the remedies provided and procedures followed by the Immovable Property Commission (henceforth, IPC or Commission) in Cyprus. It argues that any institution established to remedy forced

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[‡] T Allen and B Douglas, 'Closing the Door on Restitution: The European Court of Human Rights' in A Buysse and M Hamilton (eds), *Transitional Jurisprudence and the ECHR: Justice, Politics and Rights* (CUP, 2011).

[§] *Demopoulos and Others v. Turkey* (Application no. 46113/99) (2010) 50 E.H.R.R. SE14.

^{**} *Chiragov and Others v. Armenia* (Application no. 13216/05) (2015).

^{††} *Sargsyan v. Azerbaijan* (Application no. 40167/06) (2015).

displacement should aim to achieve two objectives: first, it should comply with human rights and second, it should work towards the unfreezing of the conflict by building trust between its different parties. Drawing lessons from the experiences of the IPC, the ECtHR's case law and other key international policy documents, the article seeks to provide guidelines for the establishment and operation of such remedying bodies. These guidelines could be useful, particularly to the governments of Armenia and Azerbaijan that are currently under an obligation to comply with the ECtHR's *Chiragov/Sargysian* judgments, but also to other countries affected by frozen conflicts in Europe and elsewhere. At the same time, this analysis remains relevant to Cyprus, whose leaders are optimistic about the outcome of the ongoing negotiations for a comprehensive peace settlement.^{‡‡} If the negotiations are successful, the experiences of the IPC could provide useful insights for the establishment of a new body that will remedy once and for all, everyone who has been displaced by the conflict on the island.

II. FROZEN CONFLICTS AND FORCED DISPLACEMENT IN EUROPE

Frozen conflicts are characterised by the eruption of violence between two or more groups, followed by a ceasefire agreement, which although results in the stopping of the altercations, does not permanently resolve the disagreement between the previously warring parties. Thus, although the situation is stable, sometimes even safe, the unresolved conflict lingers and the unsatisfactory status quo is maintained. The parties might refuse to acknowledge each other or conversely, they might participate in perpetual, yet ineffective, negotiations; in both cases however, the zero-sum nature of their disagreement makes them unable to reach a settlement for their common future. Such frozen conflicts in Europe include Cyprus, Naborno-Karabakh, Abkhazia, South Ossetia and Transnistria, with political analysts being concerned that Eastern Ukraine is also heading in the same direction.^{§§}

Each of these conflicts has its own complex history, which can only be reproduced in broad terms here. Cyprus was divided by ethnic violence between Greek and Turkish Cypriots in the 1960s and 1970s, which culminated in the 1974 Turkish invasion of the island.^{***} Since then, the different parties to the conflict have been involved in political negotiations, but they have been unable to reach a comprehensive settlement that is acceptable to both communities.^{†††} Similarly, Naborno-Karabakh, officially a part of Azerbaijan, was invaded in 1994 by Armenian and Armenian-backed forces, which have since then been in effective control of the region.^{‡‡‡} Although a ceasefire agreement has helped prevent a return to full-scale hostilities, political negotiations have not produced a permanent settlement to the conflict and some 3,000 deaths have been recorded along the front line since 1994.^{§§§} On the other hand, Abkhazia^{****} and South Ossetia^{††††} are parts of Georgia with large Russian speaking minorities, who soon after the collapse of the USSR, became involved in violent altercations with ethnic Georgians.

^{‡‡} United Nations Peacekeeping Force in Cyprus, 'Joint Statement by the Turkish Cypriot Leader Mr. Mustafa Akinci and Greek Cypriot Leader Mr. Nicos Anastasiades', available at <https://unfcyp.unmissions.org/joint-statement-turkish-cypriot-leader-mr-mustafa-akinci-and-greek-cypriot-leader-mr-nicos> [available on 29 February 2016].

^{§§} International Crisis Group (henceforth, ICG), 'Russia and the Separatists in Eastern Ukraine' (Kiev/Brussels: ICG, 2016), p 1.

^{***} *Cyprus v. Turkey* (Application no. 25781/94) (2002) 35 E.H.R.R. 30, para 13.

^{†††} MS Michael, *Resolving the Cyprus Conflict: Negotiating History* (Palgrave Macmillan, 2009).

^{‡‡‡} See note 3 above, para 13-17.

^{§§§} ICG, 'Nagorno-Karabakh: Getting to a Breakthrough' (Baku/Yerevan/Tbilisi/Brussels: ICG, 2009), p 1.

^{****} ICG, 'Abkhazia: Deepening Dependence' (Sukhumi/Tbilisi/Istanbul/Brussels: ICG, 2010), p 1.

^{††††} ICG, 'South Ossetia: The Burden of Recognition' (Tskhinvali/Tbilisi/Istanbul/Moscow/Brussels: ICG, 2010), p 1.

The situation remained stable, though tense, until 2008, when the two regions declared their independence from Georgia. Both were swiftly recognised by Russia, on which they heavily rely for military, economic and political support.^{††††} Although the conflict in Abkhazia remained mostly non-violent even in 2008, Georgian and Russian forces went to war in South Ossetia and since then, there have been no diplomatic relations between the two countries.^{§§§§} Finally, Transnistria experienced a short violent conflict between Transnistrian paramilitaries and Russian troops on the one hand, and the Moldovan army on the other, which resulted in the declaration of independence by the ‘Dniestrian Moldovan Socialist Soviet Republic’. Like with Abkhazia and South Ossetia, this entity has not been recognised internationally and remains financially and militarily dependent on Russia. Although no further violence has erupted in the region, negotiations about its future have been ongoing, yet unsuccessful, since 1993.^{*****}

These frozen conflicts share important similarities that make a comparison between them valuable. The first such similarity is that they have all resulted, to different extents, in instances of forced displacement. Approximately 45,000 Turkish Cypriots (henceforth, TC) and 165,000 Greek Cypriots (hereafter, GC) have been displaced during the conflict on the island.^{†††††} Similarly, since the beginning of the 1990s, there have been 240,000 displaced persons in Abkhazia,^{†††††} 800,000 Azeri refugees in Naborno-Karabakh,^{§§§§§} and 50,000 in Transnistria.^{*****} Moreover, the 2008 war resulted in approximately 120,000 refugees from South Ossetia,^{†††††} with some 20,000 ethnic Georgians still remaining unable to return to their houses.^{†††††} While forced displacement is a characteristic of violent contexts more generally, frozen conflicts face additional challenges to the usual ones. The most important such challenge concerns the passage of time and the fact that in the years that passed since the displacement, other people might have moved in the properties in question.^{§§§§§} The longer the period since the war, the more necessary it becomes to balance any interests the secondary occupiers might have acquired with those of the original property owners. Yet, the complexity of this balancing exercise is not reflected in the seminal UN Principles on Housing and Property Restitution for Refugees and Displaced Persons (henceforth, the Pinheiro Principles), which merely declare that ‘All refugees and displaced persons have the right to have restored to them any housing, land and/or property of which they were arbitrarily or unlawfully deprived.’^{*****} Since restitution returns the displaced population to its original position to the greatest possible extent, it is only right that it is the international community’s preferred remedy. While however, its use is uncontroversial in conflicts that have lasted for a relatively short period of time, it

^{††††} Ibid.

^{§§§§} PK Baev, ‘Russia Makes a Move in the Caucasus – and Looks Beyond’ (2008) 8 *The EU-Russia Centre Review* 64.

^{*****} ICG, ‘Moldova: No Quick Fix’ (Chisinau/Brussels: ICG, 2003), pp 3-4.

^{†††††} Global IDP Database, ‘Profile of Internal Displacement: Cyprus’ (Geneva: Norwegian Refugee Council/Global IDP Project, 2003), p 6, citing estimates of the UN Peacekeeping Force in Cyprus.

^{†††††} Global IDP Database, ‘Profile of Internal Displacement: Georgia’ (Geneva: Norwegian Refugee Council/Global IDP Project, 2005), p 6, citing estimates of the UN Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs.

^{§§§§§} See note 3 above, para 25.

^{*****} Z Brunarska and A Weinar, ‘Asylum Seekers, Refugees and IDPs in the EaP Countries: Recognition, Social Protection and Integration – An Overview’ (CARIM-East Research Report 2013/45), p 5.

^{†††††} ICG, ‘Russia v. Georgia: The Fallout’ (Tbilisi/Brussels: ICG, 2008), p 3.

^{†††††} See note 12 above, p i.

^{§§§§§} A Smit, *The Property Rights of Refugees and Internally Displaced Persons: Beyond Restitution* (Routledge, 2012), p 170.

^{*****} Sub-Commission on the Promotion and Protection of Human Rights, ‘Principles on Housing and Property Restitution for Refugees and Displaced Persons’ (Geneva: UN, 2005), Principle 2.1.

creates difficulties of principle and application in frozen conflicts.^{††††††} Examining how this balance has been struck and displacement has been remedied in one frozen conflict, can provide useful lessons about how similar questions can be addressed in another.

The second similarity between such conflicts concerns the fact that they all tend to be characterised by a lack of trust between the different groups of the population. Although frozen conflicts usually result in relatively stable conditions on the ground, uncertainty about how they will develop in the future contributes to feelings of insecurity among the public.^{††††††} In turn, this often translates to a lack of trust both towards the politicians that are negotiating the settlement and between the populations of the different parties to the conflict.^{§§§§§§} It is therefore important that if a remedying mechanism is established in such societies, especially when it is concerned with such a sensitive issue as forced displacement, it takes steps to improve trust levels between the politicians and the population and also among the people themselves. While however, ‘restoring public trust in national institutions of governance’^{*****} is among the key objectives of transitional justice, and although *post-conflict* societies often establish institutions with this mandate, trust-building has received far less attention in contexts of *frozen conflicts*.^{††††††} This is puzzling because trust-building is as important to a society that is negotiating a peace agreement, as it is to one that has already completed the negotiations and is in the process of building the common institutions that have been agreed. Peacebuilders usually focus on transitional justice mechanisms after a comprehensive peace settlement has been reached, but there is nothing that prevents parties from adopting such mechanisms before, or even in order to aid, the successful completion of the negotiation process. This was confirmed by Judge Ziemele in *Sargsyan*, when he argued that remedying the displaced people could ‘be a way of moving towards finding a solution to the conflict’.^{††††††}

Thus, and although they have rarely been perceived as such, the IPC and other remedying bodies established during frozen conflicts, should be seen and evaluated, as rather unique examples of transitional justice mechanisms.^{§§§§§§} If they are successful, such mechanisms could contribute to the unfreezing of the conflict in two ways. On the one hand, they could make a direct contribution to conflict settlement by protecting the human rights of the displaced population; in turn, this could put the victims in their original position as much as possible and allow them to eventually leave the conflict behind them.^{*****} On the other, they can make symbolic contributions to the resolution of the conflict by sending messages of reconciliation

^{††††††} See note 22 above.

^{††††††} Despite the stable status quo in Cyprus, more than 70% of GC and TC believe that security should be the ‘highest priority item’ during the peace negotiations. (A Lordos and E Kaymak, ‘Public Opinion and the Property Issue: Quantitative Findings’ (Cyprus: Interpeace, 2010).)

^{§§§§§§} See note 10 above, p 1 and 8.

^{*****} UN Secretary-General, ‘The Rule of Law and Transitional Justice in Conflict and Post-conflict Societies’ (New York: UN, 2004), para 1.

^{††††††} For example, although some confidence-building measures have been adopted in Cyprus, these have received a lot less attention by the media and the peacebuilders themselves, than the formal negotiations. (M Hadjipavlou and B Kanol, ‘Cumulative Impact Case Study: The Impact of Peacebuilding Work on the Cyprus Conflict’ (Nicosia: CDA Collaborative Learning Projects, 2008.))

^{††††††} See note 4 above, Concurring Opinion of Judge Ziemele, para 7.

^{§§§§§§} N Skoutaris, ‘Building Transitional Justice Mechanisms without a Peace Settlement: A Critical Appraisal of Recent Case Law of the Strasbourg Court on the Cyprus Issue’ (2010) 35 *European Law Review* 720.

^{*****} As the UNHRC put it, ‘[w]hen they choose voluntarily to go back to their homeland, refugees are, quite literally, voting with their feet and expressing confidence in the future of their country.’ (United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees, *The State of the World’s Refugees: A Humanitarian Agenda* (OUP, 1997), p 162.)

to the population at large.^{††††††††} When responding to forced displacement in frozen conflicts therefore, the objective should not only be to provide effective remedies in the legalistic and technical sense of the word, but also to address the root of the problem and ensure that these contribute to the betterment of inter-ethnic relations among the population at large. As Shelton put it, in cases of armed conflict ‘reparations are often a matter of compromise and look to the future as much as to the past’.^{††††††††}

The final common characteristic of frozen conflicts is that with the passage of time, the political and legal context in which they play out, changes. For instance, it was a seemingly unrelated event, Kosovo’s declaration of independence and the response of the international community to it, that caused Abkhazia and South Ossetia to declare their independence in 2008 and deepened the conflict between Georgia and the Russian Federation.^{§§§§§§§§} Similarly, Cyprus’ accession to the European Union has introduced new players and relevant considerations to the conflict, and has changed the political and economic setting in which the settlement will take place.^{*****} However, the institution that has been changing in the most dynamic way the political and legal context in which frozen conflicts are negotiated is the ECtHR. Of Europe’s frozen conflicts, two – Cyprus and Naborno-Karabakh – have resulted in decisions of the Court relating to forced displacement. The (GC) cases against Turkey, and in particular *Cyprus v. Turkey* and *Loizidou v. Turkey*,^{††††††††} are well known among the academic community.^{††††††††} In the admissibility decision of *Loizidou*, the Court reached two findings with significant implications for frozen conflicts.^{§§§§§§§§} first, that Turkey was in effective control over the north of Cyprus and therefore responsible for any violations that are taking place there; the self-declaration of the ‘Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus’ (hereafter, ‘TRNC’) as an independent state could not shield Turkey from its human rights obligations.^{*****} Second, even though the displacement of the applicant had taken place in 1974, there was a continuing interference with her right to use her property that persisted (and was renewed every day) until the violation had been remedied.^{††††††††} Both of these conclusions have been reiterated in *Chiragov*, in which the Court held that Armenia was responsible for human rights violations in Naborno-Karabkah because, like Turkey in northern Cyprus, it has been in effective control of the region.^{††††††††}

At the merits stage of *Loizidou*, the Court held that the prevention of the applicant by the Turkish military to use her property constituted a violation of the right to property under Article 1 of Protocol No. 1 (henceforth, Article 1-1) of the European Convention. This created an obligation on Turkey to remedy the applicant, not for the loss of the property itself, but for her inability to access and use it. Thus, even after she had been remedied, the applicant remained the owner of the property, an important consideration in light of the developments following the establishment of the IPC. The Court confirmed its *Loizidou* findings in *Cyprus v. Turkey*, where before finding a violation of Article 1-1, it held that it was not necessary to exhaust

^{††††††††} D Shelton, *Remedies in International Human Rights Law* (OUP, 2006, 2nd edn.), pp 16-17 and 150.

^{††††††††} *Ibid.*, p 430.

^{§§§§§§§§} See note 12 above, p 1.

^{*****} S Laulhé Shaelou, *The EU and Cyprus: Principles and Strategies of Full Integration* (Martinus Nijhoff Publishers, 2010).

^{††††††††} *Loizidou v. Turkey* (Application no. 15318/89) (1997) 23 E.H.R.R. 513 (Merits).

^{††††††††} The Cypriot conflict has also given rise to TC applications to the ECtHR. For an analysis of these, see N Hadjigeorgiou, ‘Case Note on *Kazali and Others v. Cyprus*’ (2013) 2 *Cyprus Human Rights Law Review* 103.

^{§§§§§§§§} *Loizidou v. Turkey* (Application no. 15318/89) (1995) 20 E.H.R.R. 99 (Preliminary Objections).

^{*****} *Ibid.*, para 63.

^{††††††††} See note 36 above, para 41.

^{††††††††} See note 3 above, para 186.

domestic remedies, thus granting the applicant direct access to it, because the practices of the ‘TRNC’ were discriminatory against GC and, therefore, ineffective. § § § § § § § § § § *Loizidou*’s findings were endorsed and expanded in the numerous cases with identical facts that followed, such as *Demades v. Turkey*, in which the Court held that the prevention of the applicant to access his house did not only constitute a violation of the right to property, but also of the right to home, as protected under Article 8 of the European Convention. *****

The *Loizidou* line of cases changed the context in which the Cypriot negotiations were taking place since they provided, for the first time, an authority for the view that leaving the displaced population without any remedy at all was not an option. Nevertheless, it is the case of *Xenides-Arestis v. Turkey* and the admissibility decision of *Demopoulos v. Turkey* that most vividly show the dynamic effects of the ECtHR jurisprudence. † † † † † † † † † † In *Xenides-Arestis*, Turkey argued that a newly created mechanism, the IPC, provided an effective remedy that the applicants should exhaust before having access to the ECtHR. The Court accepted the argument in principle, but ultimately held that the composition of the IPC and the remedies it was providing at the time, were in need of further improvement. It was 5 years later in *Demopoulos* that the ECtHR finally held that the amended IPC Law and the Commission it gave rise to provided effective remedies to GC applicants. † † † † † † † † † † In *Demopoulos*, the applicant and the Cypriot government that supported his claim, repeated the arguments that the Court had already dismissed in *Xenides-Arestis*, namely that the IPC could not, as a matter of principle, provide an effective remedy because it was the product of an illegal invasion and it was established by an entity that was not recognized in international law. Both arguments were again rejected by the Court, which declared that the IPC was established, not by the ‘TRNC’, but by Turkey. § § § § § § § § § § It held moreover, that the mechanisms provided by Turkey could not be by definition ineffective because that would mean that the applicants were not actually expecting the respondent state to remedy them in some way, which would render their resort to the ECtHR futile. ***** Thus, *Demopoulos* has changed the context relating to forced displacement in Cyprus because since then, applicants have had to exhaust domestic remedies, and in particular apply to the IPC in order to obtain access to the ECtHR. Whether the IPC is an ineffective remedy, not because of reasons of principle, but due to practical considerations, is not an argument that was pursued by the applicants or that has been discussed by academics since then. † † † † † † † † † † It is this gap in the literature that the subsequent analysis seeks to address.

Building on its Cypriot jurisprudence, the ECtHR has recently delivered two twin cases – *Chiragov v. Armenia* and *Sargsyan v. Azerbaijan* – both of which concern complains by persons living in Nagorno-Karabakh, who have been prevented from accessing and using their properties since the war. While the ECtHR found Armenia to be in violation because it was in

§ § § § § § § § § § See note 7 above, paras 99, 172 and 184.

***** *Demades v. Turkey* (Application no. 16219/90) (2003). For a discussion of the right to home in the context of the Cypriot conflict, see C Paraskeva and E Meleagrou, ‘Homes from the Past: An Expiration Date for the Right to Respect for Home Under Article 8 of the European Convention on Human Rights’ (2012-2013) VII *Annuaire International Des Droits De L’Homme* 845.

† † † † † † † † † † *Xenides-Arestis v. Turkey* (Application no. 46347/99) (2007) 44 E.H.R.R. SE13.

† † † † † † † † † † See note 2 above, para 90.

§ § § § § § § § § § *Ibid.*, para 95.

***** *Ibid.*, para 89.

† † † † † † † † † † The literature on *Demopoulos* has mostly dealt with the question of whether the IPC could provide effective remedies as a matter of principle, rather than practice. See, for example, E Katselli-Proukaki, ‘The Right of Displaced Persons to Property and to Return Home after *Demopoulos*’ (2014) 14 *Human Rights Law Review* 701; L Loucaides, ‘Is the European Court of Human Rights Still a Principled Court of Human Rights after the *Demopoulos* Case?’ (2011) 24 *Leiden Journal of International Law* 435; A Solomou, ‘Case Note on *Demopoulos & Others v. Turkey* (Admissibility)’ (2010) 104 *American Journal of International Law* 628.

effective control of Naborno-Karabakh, Azerbaijan's responsibility was engaged because the displacement had taken place in its internationally recognized territory, where it has an obligation to take positive actions to protect human rights.^{††††††††††} Thus, Azerbaijan restricted access to Naborno-Karabakh for legitimate reasons, namely because the area was a military sensitive zone, but it still violated the right to property because it did not compensate the displaced population in any way.^{§§§§§§§§§§} Finding both respondent states in violation of Article 1-1 and asking them to provide an effective remedy to the applicants, the Court repeated its warning from *Loizidou*, namely that the mere fact that governments were engaged in negotiations for the resolution of the conflict could not in itself excuse the absence of a legal remedy.^{*****}

The extension of the ECtHR's Cypriot jurisprudence in other frozen conflicts and the dynamic effects it could have in them suggests that assessing the practices of the IPC can be valuable for two reasons. The first is that this can contribute to the discussion about the best way to remedy forced displacement in Cyprus itself, both before and after the comprehensive peace settlement. Following *Demopoulos*, the IPC is considered as providing an effective remedy, but GC are likely to challenge this ruling and argue that the Commission's practices result in violations of the rights to property and fair trial.^{††††††††††} In such a case, a clear picture of how the IPC operates and what are the outcomes of its procedures will form the backbone of the applicants' challenge and the debate that will follow. At the same time, it is acknowledged that the Commission is only serving a temporary function of remedying displaced GC until a comprehensive settlement to the Cyprus problem is reached. After that, the IPC will likely be replaced by a different institution tasked with permanently remedying all Cypriots, whether they have been displaced from the north or the south of the island.^{††††††††††} When designing such an institution, insights about the IPC will provide invaluable sources of information.

The second reason such an analysis is valuable is because the IPC could operate as a blueprint for institutions offering remedies to people who remain displaced as a result of other frozen conflicts around Europe. While there has not been ECtHR case law concerning forced displacement in Abkhazia, South Ossetia or Transnistria, the context of these conflicts is similar enough to Cyprus to raise expectations that if an application is submitted, it will be dealt with in a similar way. This is confirmed by *Ilaşcu and Others v. Moldova and Russia*, which concerned violations of Articles 3 and 5 of the European Convention;^{§§§§§§§§§§} here, relying on *Loizidou*, the Court held that Russia's military and economic control of Transnistria render it responsible for human rights violations committed there.^{*****} Moreover, the conflict in Eastern Ukraine has given rise to an inter-state case and approximately 1,600 individual applications to the ECtHR concerning alleged violations of property rights, which are also likely to be dealt with in a similar manner to *Loizidou*.^{††††††††††} Most urgently however, a comparative analysis of the IPC is particularly useful to the governments of Armenia and Azerbaijan, which are expected to set up 'a property claims mechanism [...]

^{††††††††††} See note 4 above, para 223-226.

^{§§§§§§§§§§} *Ibid.*, para 234

^{*****} *Ibid.*, para 236-237.

^{††††††††††} The possibility of such cases reaching the ECtHR in the near future has already been reported in the Cypriot media. See, for example, Politis, 'Trouble for the IPC', 11/12/2015, available at <http://m.politis-news.com/cgi-bin/hweb?-A=309748&-V=articles> [accessed on 4 January 2016].

^{††††††††††} This is the arrangement that was proposed in the Annan Plan. (The Comprehensive Settlement for the Cyprus Problem (31 March 2004), Annex IIV, Attachment 2).

^{§§§§§§§§§§} *Ilaşcu and Others v. Moldova and Russia* (Application no. 48787/99) (2005) 40 E.H.R.R. 46.

^{*****} *Ibid.*, para 314.

^{††††††††††} ECtHR, 'Press Country Profile: Ukraine' (Strasbourg: Council of Europe, 2016), p 8.

allowing the applicants and others in their situation to have their property rights restored and to obtain compensation for the loss of their enjoyment.’^{*****} The ECtHR has urged the two governments to obtain guidance about the establishment of these mechanisms from relevant international standards, like the Pinheiro Principles and a 2010 Parliamentary Assembly resolution.^{§§§§§§§§§§§§} However, while these documents offer some general advice, interested governments are likely to obtain much more specific direction by focusing on existing remedying bodies and drawing conclusions about what should be adopted or avoided.

This analysis does not suggest that a comparison between Cyprus and other frozen conflicts is straight forward; rather, important differences can also exist between the case studies. The first such difference between Cyprus and the ex-Soviet regions stems from the communist history of the latter and the fact that many people might not have been, at the time of their displacement, the private owners of the properties in question. The second is concerned with the multiple waves of displacement, experienced for example in Abkhazia and South Ossetia both in the early 1990s and then in 2008, which are likely to result in claims to the same property from multiple potential right-holders. Despite such differences however, a careful comparison between the various conflicts could provide valuable sources of inspiration for solutions to their common problems.

III. AN ASSESSMENT OF THE REMEDIES PROVIDED BY THE IPC

The IPC was created by Law 67/2005, which gives GC who were displaced from their properties in 1974, the opportunity to be remedied for the loss they suffered.^{*****} In principle, applicants can choose from three types of remedies: payment of *compensation* for the loss of their property; its return (*restitution*); or the *exchange* of their property found in the north of the island, with a TC property of equal value in the south.^{††††††††††††} Nevertheless, in practice, the first of the three is by far the most popular: of the 752 applicants that have been remedied so far, 728 have received compensation.^{††††††††††††} If the applicant has been awarded one of the three remedies, he also becomes entitled to compensation for *loss of use* of that property from 1974 until today.^{§§§§§§§§§§§§} It is however, impossible for an applicant to request only compensation for loss of use without also claiming compensation, exchange or restitution of the property itself. Bearing in mind that the applicants who originally resorted to the ECtHR were only demanding a remedy for the loss of use of their properties, GC perceive this provision of the law as unfair. They are arguing that in essence Turkey is giving with the one hand and taking with the other since one can only become remedied for loss of use if he is willing to give up the title of the property itself (in the vast number of cases in lieu of compensation). While this might not be problematic from a human rights perspective,^{*****} it has been used by GC politicians to undermine any goodwill

^{*****} See note 3, para 199 and note 4 above, para 238.

^{§§§§§§§§§§§§} Council of Europe Parliamentary Assembly, ‘Solving Property Issues of Refugees and Internally Displaced Persons’ (Resolution 1708 (2010)).

^{*****} (‘TRNC’) Law No. 67/2005 (‘Law for the Compensation, Exchange and Restitution of Immovable Properties which are within the scope of sub-paragraph (B) of paragraph 1 of Article 159 of the Constitution’).

^{††††††††††††} Law 67/2005, Article 4(1).

^{††††††††††††} Presidency of the IPC, ‘Monthly Bulletin, February 2016’, (Nicosia: IPC, February 2016), available at http://www.tamk.gov.ct.tr/dokuman/istatistik_subat16ing.pdf [accessed on 01 March 2016], p 5.

^{§§§§§§§§§§§§} Law 67/2005, Article 8.

^{*****} See note 2 above, para 111.

must be adequately accessible and sufficiently precise.***** As a minimum requirement, it is necessary that applicants have an indication of the legal rules that apply to their case in order to foresee to a reasonable degree the consequences of their actions.†††††††††††††††† This obligation is potentially frustrated here because, in most cases, applicants remain completely in the dark about the outcome of the remedying process, namely the amount of compensation they can expect to receive. Thus, in *Hentrich v France*, the ECtHR found a law interfering with the applicant's property rights to be in violation of Article 1-1 because it 'operated arbitrarily and selectively and was scarcely foreseeable, and it was not attended by the basic procedural safeguards'.†††††††††††††††† Perhaps more problematic however, is the effect of this uncertainty in terms of how the IPC is perceived by the GC population. In particular, leaving the applicants in the dark about the compensation amount they will receive, risks disappointing them and making them feel that they have been cheated. While it is unclear whether applicants actually experience such disappointment, the high percentage of applications that have been submitted to the IPC and then subsequently revoked before a final decision has been made, is a worrisome indication. §§§§§§§§§§§§§§§§§§§§

In addition to the lack of information, assessing whether the compensation amount provided by the IPC is adequate becomes difficult due to several disagreements of principle. More specifically, the decision of whether the compensation amount falls far below the market price depends on what one understands by the 'market' in the first place.***** GC argue that in order for the applicants to be adequately remedied for their loss and return to their original position as much as possible, they must be compensated as if the Turkish invasion had never taken place. They further submit that the market prices in the north today do not really reflect the properties' true value because two external factors keep them artificially low. First, the fleeing of GC from the north due to the 1974 invasion has meant that the demand for (and therefore the market price of) properties has gone down. Second, the legal uncertainty about who is the true owner of the properties makes it less likely that foreigners will invest there, which again reduces property prices.†††††††††††††††† It is for this reason that when GC applicants were submitting estimations of the value of their properties to the ECtHR, they compared them with similar properties in the south, rather than the north, of Cyprus.†††††††††††††††† Conversely, TC argue that the market price is simply the amount for which a property can be sold today. Thus, the only relevant market in this equation should be the one that exists in the north. It is this latter approach that has been adopted both by the IPC and the ECtHR. As the Court put it in *Loizidou*, '[t]he applicant was entitled to be fully compensated for loss of access to and control of her property but not for the diminished value of that property due to the general political situation.' §§§§§§§§§§§§§§§§§§§§

Leaving aside disagreements of principle, the best way to assess the adequacy of the IPC's awards is to compare them with those of the ECtHR. This becomes possible due to a series of cases whose merits the ECtHR decided before, but whose just satisfaction it decided after,

***** *Sunday Times v. United Kingdom* (Application no. 6538/74) (1979-80) 2 E.H.R.R. 245, para 49.

†††††††††††††††† Ibid.

†††††††††††††††† *Hentrich v. France* (Application no. 13616/88) (1994) 18 E.H.R.R. 440, para 42.

§§§§§§§§§§§§§§§§ See note 61 above, para 5.

***** For a theoretical discussion of this debate, see note 32 above, p 333.

†††††††††††††††† The uncertainty of 'TRNC' titles was confirmed by the decision of the Court of Justice of the European Union in *Apostolides v Orams*, C-420/07, EU:C:2009:271.

†††††††††††††††† *Strati v. Turkey* (Application no. 16082/90) (2010), para 31.

§§§§§§§§§§§§§§§§ *Loizidou v. Turkey* (Just Satisfaction) (Application no. 15318/89) (1998) 26 E.H.R.R. CD 5, para 30.

1-1 since it involves a situation where the applicant is being deprived of his/her property, yet the State is refusing to remedy him/her in any way. ***** Equally problematic to the legal issues that arise from the treatment of the Varosha cases is the effect that this has on trust-building between the two communities. In particular, it raises questions among GC about the good faith of the IPC since it is refusing to hear those cases that are most likely to result in the granting of the applicants' preferred remedies.

IV. A PROCEDURAL ASSESSMENT OF THE IPC

A. The lack of legal clarity in the process

Equally important to the provision of remedies is ensuring that the Commission complies with clear and transparent rules of procedure. Law 67/2005 includes detailed provisions about the process one has to follow in order to be remedied by the IPC. Initially, the applicant must satisfy the Commission that he was either registered in 1974 in the RoC Land Registry as the owner of the property or that he is the legal heir of such a person. ***** Then, according to the Law, the application follows a procedure resembling that of a normal civil case. ***** The two parties – the applicant and a lawyer from the 'TRNC' Attorney-General's Office ***** – submit their arguments and '[t]he Commission, after having heard the arguments of the parties and witnesses, and having examined the documents submitted', decides on the appropriate remedy. ***** However, in practice, a hearing stage where the applicants formally present their arguments is only available in exceptional circumstances; so far, only 21 cases have followed the procedure described in Law 67/2005. *****

In the remaining 878 cases, the parties follow a long – and undocumented, but standard – procedure that is designed to lead to a friendly settlement. ***** First, the applicant submits his/her documentation and provides evidence that s/he is the owner or heir of the property. If the IPC is satisfied with this documentation, it gives a date for a 'mention meeting', which is where the friendly settlement takes place. During this meeting, the lawyer from the 'TRNC' Attorney-General's Office recommends the remedy of compensation and, based on an evaluation by the 'TRNC' Land Registry, makes an offer. The applicant is likely to make a counter-offer and a negotiation, which is overseen by three members of the IPC, takes place. If the two sides fail to agree on a negotiated amount, they can meet again in subsequent mention meetings until they reach a friendly settlement. If this proves unobtainable, the applicant can withdraw his/her application or ask that it proceeds to a hearing. In case a hearing takes place, the applicant can appeal the IPC's decision to the 'TRNC' High Administrative Court. ***** Alternatively, if a friendly settlement is

Court stated that 'the limitations [to Article 6] must not restrict or reduce the access left to the individual in such a way or to such an extent that the very essence of the right is impaired.'
 ***** This was, after all, the very basis of the Court's reasoning in *Loizidou*.
 ***** Law 67/2005, Article 6(2).
 ***** Law 67/2005, Article 16 and the Rules Made under Sections 8(2)(a) and 22 of the Law for the Compensation, Exchange and Resitution of Immovable Properties which are within the Scope of Sub-Paragraph (B) of Paragraph 1 of Article 159 of the Constitution (Law No. 67/2005), Article 9.
 ***** Law 67/2005, Article 7.
 ***** Law 67/2005, Article 8.
 ***** See note 61 above, p 5.
 ***** Ibid.
 ***** Law 67/2005, Article 9.

reached, the applicant provides up-to-date evidence that he is still the owner and approximately 12 months later, s/he signs the property away to the 'TRNC' and receives the compensation amount.

It appears therefore that rather than the IPC operating as the final decision-maker in an adjudicative process, it is acting as the facilitator to a negotiation. The argument here is not that the hearing process described in the Law is necessarily better than the method of negotiation followed in practice. Adjudication might be more transparent, but a negotiated outcome is speedier, less confrontational and more likely to be accepted by the applicants than an imposed judicial decision. Ultimately however, whether the respondent state opts for a hearing or something less formal, the preferred choice should be reflected in the law. A disparity between the legal text and what is happening on the ground results in a lack of clarity and certainty of the process, and in turn, to potential human rights violations. In particular, Article 1-1 of the European Convention requires that any interferences with the right to property are 'provided by law'. Interpreting this requirement in light of the rule of law,***** the Court has demanded not only that the interference with the right to property has a basis in national law, but also that this law is accessible, precise and foreseeable.***** It has, for example, found a violation of Article 1-1 in cases where there were inconsistencies in the process described in the law, a situation that resembles what is being described here.*

In addition to complying with its human rights obligations, a respondent state should make sure that the process followed by the remedying body is transparent for three additional reasons. First, the Pinheiro Principles have emphasized the need to ensure that the remedying process is as certain and transparent as possible.† Second, following a clearly defined procedure is important for all state institutions, but it is especially so for bodies such as the IPC, which were created precisely in order to remedy human rights violations.‡ Finally, if the remedying body is following a more transparent process, this can affect the displaced population's perceptions about the fairness, neutrality and legitimacy of the other community's institutions. In turn, such perceptions can have a positive impact on the extent to which the applicants feel truly remedied and can, therefore, influence their willingness to coexist and cooperate with members of the other community in the future.§

Related to the requirement of transparency is the notion of independence. One important way in which the 'independence, impartiality and expertise' of the remedying body can be secured is 'through appropriate rules on [its] composition that may provide for the inclusion of international members.'** The importance of the composition of the remedying body was also emphasised in *Xenides-Arestis*, in which the ECtHR demanded that the Commission should comprise of international, in addition to the existing TC, members.†† In an attempt to comply

***** *Iatrides v. Greece* (Application no. 31107/96) (2000) 30 E.H.R.R. 97, para 58.

***** *Carbonara and Ventura v. Italy* (Application no. 24638/94) (2000), para 64; *Beyeler v. Italy* (Application no. 33202/96) (2001) 33 E.H.R.R. 52, para 109.

* *Baklanov v. Russia* (Application no. 68443/01) (2005), para 46.

† See note 23 above, Principle 12.1.

‡ E Brems and L Lavrysen, 'Procedural Justice in Human Rights Adjudication: The European Court of Human Rights' (2013) 35 *Human Rights Quarterly* 176, p 185.

§ A similar point was made when assessing the practices of the South African Commission on Restitution of Land Rights. See, for example, T Roux, 'Land Restitution and Reconciliation in South Africa', in F Du Bois and A Du Bois-Pedain (eds), *Justice and Reconciliation in Post-Apartheid South Africa* (CUP, 2008).

** See note 58 above, para 10.7.

†† See note 13 above.

with this requirement, Turkey amended the original provisions of Law 67/2005 to provide that the IPC should consist of 5 to 7 members, at least 2 of whom are not Cypriots, Greeks or Turks,^{‡‡} a change which the ECtHR applauded in *Demopoulos*.^{§§} Nevertheless, it appears that the two international members, who played such an important role in rendering the IPC an effective organ in the eyes of the ECtHR, are rarely actually present. The Law states that the Commission can convene when there is a two-thirds majority, yet makes no provision for the compulsory presence of at least one of the international members. As a result, the international members tend to sit with the Commission only when there is a hearing, rather than also participate in the friendly settlement proceedings.^{***} Considering the rarity of the hearings, most applicants never have any contact with the international members at all. Drawing lessons from the Cypriot experience therefore, policy makers in frozen conflicts should be careful to not only ensure the involvement of international members on paper, but also guarantee that their actual participation is both meaningful and regular.

B. Delays in the proceedings of the IPC

The final procedural flaw that can undermine trust-building among the different parties and result in human rights violations is an unreasonable delay in the proceedings. This has been a problem for the IPC, which takes approximately 7-8 years to finalise a case that is resolved through negotiations, includes no hearing by the Commission itself and no appeal to the ‘TRNC’ Courts.^{†††} The ECtHR held in *Meleagrou v. Turkey* that the IPC is a body that should comply with Article 6 requirements, including that of providing timely access to a judicial body.^{‡‡‡} While the Court has not given a specific time frame after which Article 6 will have been violated, factors that affect the reasonableness of the delay include the complexity of the case, the applicant’s and the relevant authorities’ conduct and what was at stake in the dispute.^{§§§} IPC cases are relatively simple since all that is required is to prove ownership of the property by presenting the relevant title deeds, yet at the same time, what is at stake for the applicant is extremely important. Moreover, while the Commission has over the years been manned adequately with administrative staff and translators, the Attorney-General’s Office and the Land Registry, on which the remedying process also relies, have not. It is for example, a frequent phenomenon for applicants to appear at the IPC for scheduled mention meetings, only to be told by the administrative staff that the valuation by the Land Registry has not been completed yet or that the lawyer from the Attorney-General’s Office will not be appearing that day. Although these are not judicial organs, their delays can still cause a violation of Article 6 since according to the ECtHR’s jurisprudence, the respondent state is responsible for the actions of all public institutions.^{****} Moreover, while it is appreciated that the delays are due to these bodies’ excessive workload, this is not an excuse that the ECtHR has been willing to entertain, since it has held in the past that it ‘is for the Contracting States to organise their legal systems in such a way’ as to meet their Article 6 obligations.^{††††}

^{‡‡} Law 67/2005, Article 11(1).

^{§§} See note 2 above, paras 76-77.

^{***} See note 105 above.

^{†††} *Ibid.*

^{‡‡‡} *Meleagrou v. Turkey* (Application no. 14434/09) (2013), para 17.

^{§§§} *Frydlender v. France* (Application no. 30979/96) (2001) 31 E.H.R.R. 52, para 43. Excessive delays in the process can also result in violations of the right to an effective remedy, under Article 13 of the European Convention (*Kudla v. Poland* (Application no. 30210/96) (2002) 35 E.H.R.R. 11.

^{****} *Martins Moreira v. Portugal* (Application no. 11371/85) (1991) 13 E.H.R.R. 517, para 60.

^{††††} *Vocaturo v. Italy* (Application no. 11891/85) (1991), para 17.

Such delays are not only problematic in terms of Turkey's ECtHR obligations, but can also fuel negative perceptions about the IPC's neutrality, since they are often perceived as evidence of the institution's bad faith towards GC applicants. It is presumably for this reason that one of the most oft-repeated guidelines found in international standards is that remedying institutions should act in a 'timely' manner and adopt 'expedited procedures'.^{††††} Illustrating the detrimental effects of these delays to the trust-building process, are statements made by GC lawyers, which they potentially also shared with their clients, that the IPC's delays are caused on purpose.^{§§§§} Allegedly, this is done so that the applicants 'break' and agree to a lower compensation amount, are discouraged from asking for restitution and do not even consider challenging the IPC's decision in the High Administrative Court. Such negative depictions of TC bodies, whether true or not, feed into the already prevalent culture of mistrust of the GC community and make it more difficult for its members to perceive the IPC as legitimate and impartial. This, not only deters people from applying to the Commission, but also undermines the prospects of reaching a comprehensive political settlement to the Cyprus problem.

At least some of the accusations of the IPC's bad faith are triggered, albeit unintentionally, by the IPC itself, whose strict adherence to the letter of the law often causes further delays to the proceedings of a case. An example of such a delay concerns the obligation to provide written evidence of the applicant's name and identity before a date for the first mention meeting is scheduled. Often however, and particularly because official documents were lost during the war and had to be replaced, there might be a discrepancy in the spelling of the applicant's name between different official registers. Rather than accepting such variations as inevitable characteristics of Cypriot records and focusing on the substance of the case, the IPC requires that the applicant provides further evidence proving – beyond any reasonable doubt, rather than on the balance of probabilities – that s/he is indeed the person s/he claims to be.^{*****}

In order to address the delays of the IPC therefore, and avoid both the findings of human rights violations and the undermining of transitional justice objectives, two steps can be adopted. On the one hand, it is necessary to adequately staff both the remedying body itself, but also other governmental departments that are instrumental to the process, such as the Land Registry and the Attorney-General's Office. If such ancillary departments employ personnel that is exclusively tasked with working on the remedying process, this will drastically reduce the waiting time for each application and help build much needed expertise among state officials. On the other hand, it would be to the overall benefit of the process if the evidentiary standards that applicants have to comply with were somewhat more relaxed. This suggestion was endorsed both by the Parliamentary Assembly^{†††††} and the European Court itself when it required in *Chiragov* and *Sargsyan* that the respondent states establish mechanisms that are 'easily accessible and provide procedures operating with flexible evidentiary standards.'^{††††††}

V. CONCLUSION

Remedying victims of forced displacement in frozen conflicts is important, not only because this forms part of the relevant states' human rights obligations, but also because a satisfactory response to the violation can prepare a disillusioned and mistrustful population for a pending

^{††††} See note 58 above, paras 10.1 and 10.6 respectively.

^{§§§§} See note 105 above.

^{*****} Law 67/2005, Article 6(2).

^{†††††} See note 58 above, para 10.6.

^{††††††} See note 3, para 199 and note 4, para 238.

peace agreement. Even though there are international standards that provide some guidance about the establishment of such remedying bodies, both they and the pronouncements of the ECtHR on this issue remain rather general and vague. Conversely, examining the experiences of a remedying body in practice can provide more detailed insights on how it, and similar institutions in other contexts, can be improved. In Europe alone, the lessons drawn from an assessment of the IPC are important due to their potential for being transplanted in Nagorno-Karabakh, South Ossetia, Abkhazia, Transnistria and even Eastern Ukraine. At the same time, examining the Commission's strengths and weaknesses could provide useful lessons for Cyprus itself. On the one hand, the IPC could be used as a blueprint for the creation of a remedying body *after* a comprehensive settlement to the Cyprus problem has been agreed; on the other, a better understanding of the Commission's outcomes and procedures could lead to their improvement *until* such a settlement is reached.

In light of the twin objectives that a remedying body should satisfy – complying with human rights and helping build trust between the previously warring parties – policy makers should consider carefully the remedies that will be made available to the applicants. More specifically, there are important practical and principled reasons why the remedy of exchange should be avoided altogether, while the remedy of restitution should become more readily available. Moreover, since compensation will probably be the most popular remedy, it is important that the award reflects, at least to some extent, the market value of the property. This award should also be accompanied in each case with an explanation of how it was calculated, a step that could increase levels of trust and acceptance of the remedying body's decisions among the displaced population. Equally important is the attention that should be paid to the procedures followed by the remedying bodies. In particular, the law should accurately reflect the process through which the applicants are remedied in practice and make provisions for the regular and meaningful participation of international members in the decision-making process. Finally, practical steps should be taken to ensure the swift remedying of the applicants, both by adequately staffing relevant government departments and by adopting more flexible evidentiary standards. A remedying body that complies with these guidelines does not in itself comprehensively resolve the frozen conflict; it does however, indicate the existence of good faith that can make a peace agreement both possible and sustainable.